

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

HEALTH CARE IN THE CITY OF KOSTANAY FROM THE END OF THE 19TH CENTURY TO 1936

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Abstract

The article deals with the formation and development of medical institutions in the Kustanai district. Construction of medical facilities, provision of qualified personnel, medical equipment, and medicine. The medicine of the Kustanai district started with one doctor, and now it has grown to the Kustanai zemstvo (regional) hospital. This article will be useful to scientists, teachers, and students of humanitarian educational institutions studying the historical direction.

Keywords: Kustanai zemstvo hospital, medical institutions, the first Kazakh doctor Mukhammedzhana Karabayeva, medical personnel, sanitary situation, diseases among the population.

The history of the city of Kustanay originates in the pre-revolutionary period. Because of the administrative-territorial changes, the issue of creating a county and a city, the administration of the Russian Empire proceeded from the expediency of the functioning of an administrative unit, starting from observing the precise work of the local administrative staff, mail, telegraph, education, and medicine. The remoteness of the administrative centre made it difficult to fulfil these issues.

"On October 21, 1868, the government of Emperor Alexander II issued the "Temporary Regulation on the Administration in the Steppe Regions of the Orenburg and West Siberian Governor General." By this document, the Orenburg Governor-Generalship was divided into two regions - the Urals and the Turgai. The process of administrative arrangement of Kazakhstan was developed in the 60s of the XIX century. It was initiated by the order of the Orenburg Governor-General N.A. Kryzhanovsky dated November 27, 1868, on the creation of Iletsk (Aktobe), Irgiz, Turgai, and Nikolaev (Kostanay) counties on the territory of the Turgai region. The area of the Turgai region was 418.138 sq. versts, more than half of which were in the Turgai and Nikolaev counties (241, 338 sq. versts). The Nicholas County was finally formalised in March 1869. Its population consisted exclusively of indigenous people and lived in eight volosts. However, the county did not have a single settled point where it would be possible to establish a county administration, so it was placed outside not only the county, but also the Turgai region in the Cossack village of Nikolaevskaya " [1].

The presence of the county administration outside the controlled territory soon became clear, as it introduced a number of inconveniences into its activities. Because the Nikolaevskaya village was located more than 100 miles from the postal route, this made it difficult not only to communicate with the regional authorities with the county administration, but also delayed the collection and transfer of the wagon tax to the cashier's office (located in Troitsk). Governor-General N.A. Kryzhanovsky, understanding the complexity of the sit-

uation, took it into account and, on October 3, 1869 allowed the transfer of the Nikolaev district administration to the city of Troitsk " [2].

The eyes of specialist scientists and officials fall on the Kustanai tract, which compares favourably with the proximity of running water and the absence of marsh lakes. The previously proposed Urdabai tract did not meet the sanitary and hygienic standards for the location of settlements. In December 1879, Governor-General N.A. Kryzhanovsky agreed to the construction of the settlement of Kustanai. Kustanai has led its history as the regional centre of the Kustanai district and region since that time.

The issue of the location of the city has been resolved, and its construction has begun. The bulk of its inhabitants were the indigenous population, as well as peasant migrants from various provinces of the Russian Empire, mainly from Samara, Voronezh, Saratov, Oryol, and Kharkov. Fertile land drew people to the territory of Kustanay and the county [3]. With difficulty, but gradually, the development of Kustanai took place, and with it other everyday needs began to arise in parallel (in the purchase of various household items, clothing, equipment for agriculture and animal husbandry, the need for building materials, as well as to teach children and treat the population, with the latter as things were not so good).

At first, "district paramedic Podolsky" worked in Kustanai, supplying the district with the necessary medicines, and since 1882, the examination of all patients in the district was carried out by the doctor Flerov, who was in the city of Troitsk. The problem in medical care was acute[4]." In the city and county, there were diseases of a different nature, the population was treated with "folk remedies," healers, povetukhs, shamans, and other representatives of alternative medicine flourished. The residents themselves were also backward in terms of medical competence.

Medical workers constantly sent reports to officials to resolve the issue with medical personnel, specially assigned and equipped buildings, and medicines. So the Nikolaev (Kostanay) county doctor P. Lapshin sent a report to the Turgai regional doctor Neymar on

the state of medical care in the county in 1886, which had about 112 thousand people in the county and one doctor and one assistant, with such a state of rapid response and high-quality provision of medical services being out of the question. They worked for wear and tear; they had to leave on their own since the peasants themselves could not get there or did not attach great danger to diseases. Approximately 612 people, of whom 271 were of the Kyrgyz class and 341 were settlers, constantly turned to the county doctor, who was subordinate to only one felder, for help. According to the types of disease, diseases of the motor organs were in the first place, followed by diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, cough, fever, and rheumatic suffering.

On March 18, 1888, their own national medical personnel appeared, and the military governor of the Turgai region, Ya. Barabash, appointed "the county doctor in the settlement of Kustanai with the rights of public service and the title of doctor, a graduate of Kazan University, Mukhammedzhan Karabaev [5]." In the face of M. Karabaev, we have a man of extraordinary destiny. He comes from a poor family that lived in village No. 4 of the Ken-Aral volost of the Nikolaev district. He was lucky; the smart boy was noticed by I. Altynsarin, who during this period of time began to actively promote education. He helped me enter the Trinity Men's Gymnasium and then the Medical Faculty of the University of Kazakhstan. A difficult time of study, constantly on the verge of a poor existence, the scholarship was small, and "the parents ... are so poor that there is not the slightest possibility of helping this student from them,[6]" and no matter how difficult it was, he graduated from the university successfully. Karabaev M. travels around the villages, provides medical care, and knows the problems of ordinary people firsthand. He practised medicine not only in the Kustanai district, but also in the Yakutsk region, where he treated leprosy patients. He worked hard, did not grumble, and gave his all to the people.

At that time, the hospital consisted of four beds, and the state of medical care for the young physician had him very worried. This issue was constantly raised, and he wrote letters and reports. The increase in population required a different position in medicine.

In 1891, the Turgai region, which included four counties (Irgiz, Iletsk, Turgai, and Nikolaev (Kostanay)), 10 people, 13 paramedics, and 4 midwives. On the eve of World War I, Kustanai had four doctors (men), five felders (four men and one woman), one midwife, and five pharmacists (pharmacies): Schiffner, Vdovin, Tabakov, and Kazimirov. It became possible to use the services of the dentist Trachtenberg[7]."

There was no civil hospital in the region, so the zemstvo, after conferring, decided to build a hospital with 15 beds in the Kustanai district and applied to the Ministry of Internal Affairs with a petition. The construction style of the zemstvo hospital building corresponded to the then-characteristic eclectic style with modern elements of the early twentieth century, made of red brick. The building, according to architectural theory, was supposed to be "two-story, rectangular, made of bricks on a strip foundation of rubble stone.

There is an entrance in the form of a portal on the northern facade, which has asymmetrical risalits. Between the windows of the first and second floors, there is a two-row fastening that encircles the entire building along the perimeter. The asymmetry in the layout, the broken forms of the parapet indicate the partial use of Art Nouveau elements [8]."

When the hospital was built in December 1912, the interior was unfinished. Due to a lack of funds from the government loan for public works, the construction was temporarily suspended. They were waiting for the allocation of additional funds from the Turgai governor in the amount of 19536 rubles for the completion of the outpatient clinic, hospital building, and services. By the beginning of 1913, the construction of the zemstvo hospital was completed, and on the facade of the building, the builders laid out a brick cottage to complete the construction.

According to the budget, one patient was fed at the rate of 4 rubles 65 kopecks. For that period, it was a sufficient amount of maintenance, since the main products (meat, vegetables, and milk) were replenished at the expense of subsidiary farming. However, there were supply interruptions in sugar, bread, fats, and other food supplies. From the side of the citizens, there were criticisms about the lack of dietary nutrition, a nurse who monitored dietary nutrition, and a qualified cook. In addition to medical buildings and outbuildings (garage, carpentry workshop, glacier, livestock base and several cold barns). In the future, the medical complex grew, living quarters for the head doctor, 3 doctors, and a groom were added. A park was laid out on the territory for the patients to rest. The presence of a pharmacy helped fully provide the hospital and citizens with the necessary medicines. The laundry fully served the needs of the hospital, maintaining sanitary and hygienic standards. New buildings were added, a new kitchen, a pantry for food with a well-equipped vegetable store, and an office. Interruptions with electricity began to be provided by the power plant, from which all the buildings were powered, including the X-ray room, the physio room, and the water supply from the well. The presence of a subsidiary farm on 1400 hectares of land 20 kilometres from the city, with all outbuildings, inventory, and machinery, livestock (37 horses, 91 cattle, 137 small cattle, 103 pigs). A 12-hectare irrigated garden provided year-round fresh vegetables and herbs.

In the Turgai region, there were 4 military infirmaries that, in addition to serving soldiers and officers of the military garrison, private individuals could use for a fixed fee. The place of reception of outpatients was the emergency room in Kustanai, which was under the "management of the city doctor." It also housed inpatients. In addition, the reception was conducted by doctors in their apartments. The financial issue for the peasants was very acute, the lack of the necessary amount for a doctor's appointment could be fatal. Therefore, civilian medical facilities were important for the common population. At the end of the 19th and 20th centuries, cases of the progression of an acutely infec-

tious disease became more frequent: smallpox, measles, scarlet fever, whooping cough, influenza, diphtheria, and typhoid fever.

"By the beginning of the 20th century, the county health department, located on Bolshoi Street (now Al-Farabi Avenue), house 53 (this is the house of the former merchant Davydov), was actively operating in Kustanai and the district. All the private pharmacies available at that time were municipalized, and medicines were transferred under the auspices of the pharmaceutical department. During the establishment of Soviet power and the period of the civil war, they suffered from a constant change of power, especially the "whites" from the Lvov and Valeryanov hospitals. Kolchak took out everything he could. Meanwhile, there was a typhus epidemic in the county; the sick lay on the floor, schools were closed due to a lack of hospital beds; teachers, older students were mobilised to collect linen for hospitals, food, beds, and everything that residents could share with the sick. For example, already in 1919-1920, high school students and teachers of the gymnasium of the city of Kustanay continued to help hospitals by working as nurses" [9].

"In 1920, the Kustanai district included the 1st Soviet, 2nd Soviet, epidemic, children's, Semiozernaya, Borovsky, Valeryanovsky, Lvov hospitals, and 37 paramedical stations. On February 10, 1920, the first disinfection chamber arrived in Kustanai. The military commissar announced to the population - residents, "who had patients with typhus (recovered and died), to bring their clothes and accessories in bags and bundles to the disinfection chamber for treatment with flowing steam. Things won't get damaged." With the acquisition of disinfection chambers, there has been a decline in the epidemic"[10].

On July 2, 1921, an Extraordinary Sanitary Commission for the Fight against Cholera was established under the Kustanai Gubernia Executive Committee, under the leadership of the Chairman of the Gubernia Executive Committee, Miroshnik. And the Kustanai city district administration issued a decree requiring citizens to report all those who became ill, or the discovery of a sick person in a house that was not reported, or they would be held liable under wartime laws. Doctors did a lot of educational work, explaining the basics of hygiene and cleanliness. In the ups and downs of political changes, no one particularly followed the cleanliness of the city. Going into any courtyard, walking along the streets, one could see heaps of garbage, manure, some rubbish, and garbage. This clearly increased the appearance of various forms of contagious diseases, or epidemics. The authorities appeal to the population to start fighting garbage on their own, by virtue of preventing an outbreak of diseases. Not all residents of the city had access to drinking water, so the construction of a water supply system was very important for the city.

In 1922-1923, there were 13 medical institutions in Kustanai Uyezd. In Kustanai, the 1st Soviet surgical hospital, designed for 30 beds, and the 2nd Soviet children's, epidemic, and prison hospitals in the districts Denisovskaya, Adamovskaya, Lvovskaya, Valeryanovskaya, Fedorovskaya, Uritskaya, Borovskaya,

Semiozernaya hospitals. Surgical operations were performed 4 times a week in the 1st Soviet and 2 times a week in the 2nd Soviet. The head of the 2nd Soviet hospital was Koltsov V.V., Gorsky Valentin Dmitrievich, who headed the 1st Soviet hospital (in 1925-26 he simultaneously headed the district health department and was in charge of the 1st Soviet hospital, being an intern surgeon of the same hospital, On July 2, 1945, he was awarded the Order of Lenin for fulfilling the government's task for the treatment of Red Army soldiers), head of the epidemic hospital Girsh A. L., head of the children's hospital Preobrazhensky V. M., Pizhanchikov I. G., Shurupov A. I., Baranov N. V., Bakhtiyarova F. A., Uspenskaya E. V. People of that period were well-known, with extensive experience working in different conditions.

Of course, in comparison with how the medical business in the county began and how it was at the beginning of 1925, there was a big difference, but still, not all types of diseases were covered and, accordingly, services for citizens. There was a need for vision specialists, gynecologists, and surgeons, so on January 15, 1923, the Eye Detachment arrived from the People's Commissariat of Health and began work. It operated a separate outpatient clinic and an inpatient department. Attendance at the eye outpatient clinic is up to 60 people initially and 300 people repeatedly per day. On April 5, 1923, a new maternity hospital with 20 beds was opened. It was well equipped with everything necessary for that period in difficult financial conditions.

In 1924, after the death of Lenin, the 2nd Soviet Hospital was named after the leader of the revolution. On February 2, 1924, archival documents for the first time mentioned the hospital. Lenin. On March 1, 1924, by a resolution of the city council, this hospital was transferred to the budget of the city council with the renaming "city hospital named after Lenin. Its staff consisted of six people: the head, who is also a therapist, a gynecologist, an eye specialist, a surgeon, an assistant, and a trainee doctor. Heating was carried out on 50 stoves, and there were 2 horses on the farm. Meals were provided for 35 kopecks per bedday. The doctor's salary was 125 rubles a month.

Personnel changes were common; advanced training or other planned tasks were assigned to doctors; the need to replenish with new specialists, for example, in connection with the departure of the head of the 1st Soviet hospital, Gorsky, for advanced training in Leningrad on April 1, 1924, instead of him being the head of the hospital and consulting at the hospital. Lenin appointed Dr. A. Preobrazhensky. On January 23, 1924, he became the head of the 2nd Soviet hospital named after him. Lenin appointed Dr. Matusevich. Since August 1, 1925, he has simultaneously served as a traveling doctor for the insurance fund. On January 19, 1926, Gorsky transferred the affairs of the head of the district health department to Mishin. At the same time, the head of the medical department of the hospital. Lenin Preobrazhensky was appointed head of the entire hospital. Lenin. This hospital, in essence, was of regional significance, since a large contingent of patients came from the regions [11]."

On February 2, 1926, due to the old age of the doctor of the Borovsk hospital, Karabaev, the doctor Rys was sent to check the physical condition of Karabaev with the provision of a report on the fact. As is known from the documents, Karabaev healed his countrymen until 1927; he died in 1928.

With the formation of the Kustanai region in July 1936, the functions of the body controlling medical institutions were taken over by the regional department of health, headed by Ryabitsky. Radchenko was appointed chief physician of the regional hospital named after Lenin. The Lenin Hospital served as a city and regional hospital until 1958.

By the beginning of the next administrative-territorial transformation (1936, when the Kustanai district became a region), Kustanai medicine had made good achievements; the presence of a number of hospitals in the region, diverse medical specialists, and funding from the centre allowed medicine to function normally in the region. Further tests of medical personnel will come during the Great Patriotic War, which will again allow doctors and medical personnel to show their knowledge, courage, and heroism in rescuing soldiers and civilians. The Kustanai region will become a deep rear, which will predetermine the fate of this region.

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